

BOOK REVIEW

The Six Faces of Globalization

Who Wins, Who Loses, and Why It Matters

Anthea Roberts & Nicolas Lamp

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Globalization, a process of growing interconnectedness between nations worldwide, has consistently evoked strong emotions and divergent viewpoints (Friedman, 2005; Stiglitz, 2017). International business (IB) scholars have actively participated in these debates, studying the effects of increased economic integration, evaluating the appropriate level of globalization promotion, and proposing strategies to mitigate any adverse effects (e.g., Akhter, 2004; Kobrin, 2017; Kobrin, 2020; Lévi, 2007). These discussions, however, have done little to quell the seemingly irreconcilable views that different groups of people have adopted about globalization, with some viewing it as essential for a sustainable future and others putting it at the heart of today's societal problems.

The award-winning book “The Six Faces of Globalization: Who Wins, Who Loses, and Why it Matters”, written by Anthea Roberts and Nicolas Lamp, argues that exploring the fault lines that divide prevailing views on globalization is essential to bring people together. In the words of the authors, “we will not tell you what to think about economic globalization. Instead, we try to show how we can think about the current controversies over economic globalization”. They do this by masterfully exploring the sophisticated arguments that underpin six leading narratives for or against globalization (and in the end even more than six). This analysis can become an important reference work for IB scholars who are interested in the heterogeneous effects of globalization on different

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stakeholders (Van Zanten & Van Tulder, 2020) and in the underlying narratives that these stakeholders develop about multinational enterprises (MNEs) and their activities (Rašković, 2022).

Using the metaphor of a scrambled Rubik's cube, the book provides six competing narratives (the cube's faces) about the winners and losers of globalization. The *Establishment Narrative*, closely aligned with the liberal view of international organizations and traditional IB scholarship (e.g., Contractor, 2021), provides a cheerleader perspective of global integration. It emphasizes the positive outcomes resulting from international trade, such as economic growth, poverty reduction, and peace. At the same time, it downplays the negative effects such as on income distribution. When challenged, Establishment proponents argue that the benefits of globalization need to be communicated better, that the alternatives to free trade are inferior (e.g., tariffs are costly), and that addressing globalization's adverse distributional impact can be achieved through domestic trade adjustment policies (e.g., wage insurance and training programs).

Roberts and Lamp also discuss three distinct anti-globalization narratives that are rooted in the perception of unequal distributional implications arising from globalization. The *Left-Wing Populist Narrative* suggests that the rules of the globalization game have been purposefully designed to benefit the local elites (the top one percent) at the expense of the masses, resulting in increased class inequality. The *Right-Wing Populist Narrative* contends that globalization has mainly benefited foreigners (the external other) at the expense of once-flourishing economic regions and their blue-collar workers. It laments the offshoring of manufacturing jobs, the onshoring of immigrants, and the decline of traditional communities and values. The *Corporate Power Narrative* argues that MNEs are the winners of globalization at the expense of workers who are exploited around the globe.

The book presents two other anti-globalization narratives that focus on threats that come from the high global interdependence that globalization generates. The *Geoeconomic Narrative* argues that the main benefactor of globalization has been China at the expense of the West. It contends that economic interdependence with China is a dangerous gamble and calls for economic decoupling, a topic that has also received growing attention in IB research (Cui, Vertinsky, Wang, & Zhou, 2023; Evenett & Pisani, 2023). The *Global Threats Narrative* worries that economic interdependence has exposed our societies to systemic threats such as global warming and pandemics.

Seeing globalization as a lose-lose scenario, Global Threats proponents call on policymakers to develop a more resilient and sustainable future that is regenerative and distributive.

The book goes beyond shedding light on the multifaceted impact of globalization. The authors argue that integrating insights from various narratives can help develop a more holistic view of the phenomenon and identify where compromises can be achieved across perspectives. They propose the adoption of a kaleidoscopic view in this regard: Every time one turns a kaleidoscope, one sees a new perspective of the different pieces that create a specific phenomenon. A kaleidoscopic view suggests that policy responses should not favor one narrative over another. Instead, it encourages a universal approach that considers multiple viewpoints, allowing for more nuanced and effective policy formulation. Li, Van Assche, Fu, Li, and Qian (2022), for example, have used this approach to identify policy areas where China, the United States and host countries can find common ground in the geopolitically contentious Belt and Road Initiative.

The kaleidoscopic perspective highlights an aspect of globalization that advocates of the Establishment Narrative have disregarded: it considers different perspectives and aims to find common grounds. For example, IB scholarship habitually emphasizes the good side of MNEs such as providing jobs, growing income, the transfer of competitive and environmental-friendly standards, or the contribution to a more peaceful society (e.g., Blomström & Kokko, 1998; Oetzel & Miklian, 2017; Reade, McKenna, & Oetzel, 2019). The negative facets of globalization receive decidedly less airtime. For example, it is only recently that IB scholarship has considered the role that MNEs and global value chains have played in driving populism (Rodrik, 2018); that it has analyzed the relation between IB and income inequality (Van Der Straaten, Narula, & Giuliani, 2023); or that it investigated the contribution of MNEs to climate change (Christmann & Taylor, 2001). The *Journal of International Business Policy* can be a good place for scholars to carefully consider the intricate relation between IB and societal problems, both the good and bad sides of it, and to discuss the implications it entails for public policy.

As already hinted at earlier, Roberts and Lamp actually provide more than six narratives about the winners and losers of globalization. They openly declare that their six main narratives are Western perspectives (as is obvious from the geoeconomic narrative that considers

China to be the benefactor of globalization at the expense of the West). In some of the later chapters, the authors worked together with a variety of local and foreign sources to articulate several non-Western narratives: the *Neocolonial Narrative* describes the Western dominance in international institutions that imposes policies and economic systems on developing countries; the *Narratives on the rise of Asia* highlights the positive association of Asia with economic globalization and Asia as being the center of the global economy; the *Narratives against Western Hegemony* focuses on Russia and China who criticize the West's intention to propagate liberal democracy and market-led capitalism as the mainstream systems. A discussion of these non-Western narratives serves as a great reminder for IB research to recognize the importance of studying public policy perspectives outside of Western developed nations (e.g., African countries), which have remained underrepresented in IB policy scholarship (Zoogah, Degbey, & Elo, 2023). For example, it can help uncover the concern among least developed countries (LDCs) that Western environmental policies such as the EU's Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism may further exclude LDCs from the global trading system (Van Assche, 2023). In addition, it can push IB scholars to reflect more carefully on how governments in third countries evaluate geopolitical tensions between China and the US, and how this influences their policy actions. Finally, it provides deeper insights into how national policy makers and supra-national institutions need to approach emerging tensions in the globalization debates. In sum, it opens up a plethora of new questions that provide relevant avenues for future research.

The book refers to several issues that will likely dominate globalization narratives in the years to come. Several of them have also recently received attention in IB policy research such as migration (Kunczer, Lindner, & Puck, 2019), global value chains (Pietrobelli, Rabellotti, & Van Assche, 2021), and uncertain environments (Devinney, Hartwell, Oetzel, & Vaaler, 2023). Roberts and Lamp, however, highlight two emerging phenomena that they deem will be most influential in the future: geopolitics and climate change. Agreeing with the book's assessment, IB policy research should bring a kaleidoscopic perspective to geopolitics and climate change. Yet, existing research remains one-sided and to a large degree merits attention to monetary values (i.e., economic wealth) over non-monetary values (e.g., living in a healthy environment and the feeling of security). The book, however, encourages us to find out which values are more relevant in what areas, for what

groups, in what situations, and to discuss the trade-offs between monetary and non-monetary goals, such as national security versus economic progress or the reaching of climate goals versus the economic progress (or loss) of particular areas or groups. Following a more pluralist approach, future research could therefore also examine in greater detail how the economic progress that MNEs can bring stands in tension with geopolitical conflicts and climate change, or how on the contrary, this economic progress can lead to a relaxation of geopolitical conflicts and a slowing down of climate change.

Besides, the book points to the relevance of narratives because they tell us something about what policy makers think and might do in the end. For example, left- and right-wing populists often target (verbally and in written form) foreign MNEs as working against the people and therefore trigger a negative sentiment against foreign MNEs in the local population (Stevens, Xie, & Peng, 2016). The questions that arise out of this are what the consequences would be for international collaborations between firms from different countries or MNE location choice? Also what happens when this rhetoric changes and when there are conflicting viewpoints that lead to a larger divide in society between “us” and “them” – a development we observe these days in populist rhetoric? How should MNEs deal with this type of uncertainty? Which viewpoint should MNEs follow and listen to in order to make reliable predictions about future developments? And can MNEs also trigger the development of a specific narrative and a potential political ideology? Despite some engagement with narratives (e.g., Gertsen & Søderberg, 2011; Thakur-Weigold & Miroudot, 2023), the book shows that there is still room for further exploration of their relevance. Hence, IB researchers should be more aware of narratives as part of informal (supranational) institutions (Hartmann, Lindner, Müllner, & Puck, 2022) – because what people say matters.

Roberts and Lamp provide a book that is not only relevant to academic scholars but also to the general public. The book provides a more diversified view on the “goods” and the “bads” of globalization. It brings an empathy to this complex issue that is needed for such “wicked” problems (Rašković, 2022) and helps to see political behavior with different eyes. The book “encourages us to step into the shoes of the proponents of narratives with which we disagree“, and suggests more integrative thinking, diverse teams, and value pluralism to be able to integrate the insights from the

different narratives. More future research on these specific suggestions and more interdisciplinarity in research topics and teams could be a good start to achieve this.

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